

Increasing phosphorus plant availability from P-rich ashes and biochars by acidification with sulfuric acid

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ABSTRACT

Biochars and ashes derived from thermal treatment of P-rich wastes could be used as bio-based fertilizers to improve P recycling. However, thermal treatments often result in low plant P availability. Acidification of these materials before soil application could potentially increase plant P availability. Based on the water-extractable P levels obtained in titration experiments, sulfuric acid concentrations between 2.5 M and 10 M were applied to digestate solids char and ash (DS-C, DS-A), poultry litter ash (PL-A), insect frass char (IF-C), sewage sludge char and ash (SS-C, SS-A) and meat and bone char (MB-C). Acidified and untreated materials were applied in a pot experiment with maize in ³³P labeled soil to determine fertilizer P uptake. The acidification resulted in a significant increase in P solubility. The amount of acid required depended on the materials' buffer capacity and P speciation. Based on XRD analysis, we assume that mainly Ca-associated P was solubilized. In the pot experiment, acidified materials outperformed untreated materials and the unfertilized control in terms of biomass and P uptake. The P recovery from the acidified materials ranked in the order DS-C > SS-A > PL-A > IF-C > DS-A > SS-C > MB-C. The acidification did not significantly decrease soil pH, nor was there an effect on plant heavy metal availability. In conclusion, acidification increased plant growth and P uptake without affecting plant heavy metal uptake and soil pH. Therefore, acidification to increase the P fertilizer value of ashes and chars is a promising approach to facilitate P recycling.

1. Introduction

Mineral phosphorus fertilizers are produced from non-renewable fossil resources. Furthermore, there is an imbalance in the geographical distribution of fossil P reserves and the future global phosphorus security will depend on only a few countries, mainly Morocco [14]. Due to its economic importance and potential supply issues, the European Union added phosphate rock to the list of Critical Raw Materials in 2014 [21]. From a European and global perspective, it is therefore essential to recover and recycle phosphorus more efficiently [20]. On the other hand, in regions with intensive livestock production, feed imports and the associated application of P-rich manure results in oversupply and accumulation of P in soil [51]. To address the regional imbalances and facilitate P recycling, P resources need to be concentrated so that they can be easily and cost-effectively transported out of these regions [61]. Another problem with common secondary P sources such as animal manure, digestate, sewage sludge or slaughterhouse waste is that they

may contain organic and microbial pollutants and heavy metals [18].

The thermal treatment of secondary P resources can provide several benefits, such as reducing waste volume and increasing P concentration, which facilitates the transport and redistribution of nutrients [38]. It can also remove volatile heavy metals, reduce heavy metal plant availability and destroy organic and microbial pollutants [69]. Another advantage of thermal treatments is that energy can be recovered from waste materials [60]. For these reasons, incineration (combustion) and pyrolysis (thermal conversion in the absence of oxygen) are becoming increasingly common waste treatments. In the case of biochar (a charcoal-like product of pyrolysis processes), field application can have further advantages due to its unique chemical and physical characteristics, such as its high content of recalcitrant carbon. Biochar application enhances soil carbon sequestration and can potentially act as a negative emission technology [66]. In addition, biochar application to soil can lead to an increase in crop yield, especially on nutrient-poor, acidic or sandy soils, due to an increase in water-holding capacity, soil pH and nutrient

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retention [34].

However, a major drawback of thermal treatments and a barrier to efficient P recycling is that they typically reduce solubility, and therefore plant availability, of P in the materials compared to their respective feedstocks. This is evident for a range of materials such as digestate solids biochar [7], sewage sludge ash [43,44], sewage sludge biochar [1, 35,52] and poultry litter ash [12]. The availability of phosphorus after thermal treatment depends on various process conditions such as process temperature, retention time and the incinerator type [24,68]. In addition, soil properties such as pH, soil texture or P sorption capacity can have a major impact on the P availability from biochars and ashes [31,67].

The low P availability in these materials is related to the formation of more insoluble P species during thermal treatment, in particular Ca-phosphates, which are the most common P forms in incinerated or pyrolyzed sewage sludge, meat and bone meal, biogas digestate or poultry litter [38]. Specifically, dicalcium phosphate, tricalcium phosphates (whitlockite) and various forms of apatite (hydroxyapatite, apatite) and calcium aluminum phosphate are present in these biochars and ashes [38]. Especially tricalcium phosphates and apatite are known to have a low plant availability, and with increasing temperatures during the process, Ca-phosphate compounds become more crystalline and less soluble [32]. Al and Fe phosphates can be present in sewage sludge ash and biochar, as well as in digestate biochar [38] and their solubility depends on the specific P speciation and the degree of crystallinity [64].

Considering the low P availability, the efficient use of biochars and ashes as secondary P resources to substitute P fertilizer and – in the case of biochar – to sequester C in soil requires P extraction or approaches to increase the P availability of the materials. Various inorganic or organic acids have been tested for the extraction of P from carcass ash [13], and piggy waste ash [39], based on the solubilization of Ca-associated P when the pH of the ashes is lowered by acid addition [39,57]. Sulfuric acid is commonly used to solubilize P from mono-incinerated sewage sludge in wet chemical extraction approaches [57]. The extraction of P from sewage sludge ash can already be performed on a larger scale [11], but is often not economically feasible [46].

Here, we propose the direct soil application of acidified P-rich biochars and ashes, which – if proven effective – could be developed into a simple, low-tech solution to increase the P fertilizer effect, especially for materials with a predominance of Ca-phosphates. However, the application of acid may solubilize elements other than P (Ito et al., 2013), which would counteract the suitability of acid-treated materials with high heavy metal (HM) contents as a phosphorus fertilizer. For untreated biochars, HM availability is often reduced with increasing pyrolysis temperature [47], and, in contaminated soils, biochar can be an effective tool to immobilize heavy metals [9]. This ability to adsorb HM has been described to be even higher after acidification [73]. Thus, in contrast to ash, acidifying biochar could have a less severe impact on HM bioavailability due to the increased stability of HM in biochars and the potential of HM sorption to the biochar.

The overall objective of this study was to investigate whether acidification could be used as an approach to increase the phosphorus availability from biochars and ashes derived from various P-rich wastes. More specifically, the objectives were to find a simple sulfuric acid acidification process that increases the P extractability of biochars and ashes, to identify materials that respond well to acidification and to evaluate the effect of acidified materials on plant P uptake, soil pH and heavy metal uptake. The following hypotheses were tested: (1) The addition of sulfuric acid to ashes and chars to pH below a certain threshold will lead to significantly increased availability of phosphorus. (2) This effect will be more pronounced in materials with a higher Ca/P ratio indicating a higher proportion of phosphorus bound to calcium. (3) Application of acidified materials to the soil will increase plant P uptake and biomass. (4) The application of acidified biochars and ashes will decrease soil pH and increase heavy metal uptake from ashes, but not from biochars.

2. Materials & methods

2.1. Materials

The chemical properties and elemental compositions of the materials used in this study are displayed in Table 1. Three ashes and four biochars were selected to represent different thermally treated P-rich organic waste streams, i.e. digestate from a biogas plant, sewage sludge from a wastewater treatment plant, meat and bone meal, insect frass and poultry litter. The digestate solid fraction was sampled from the Limfjordens biogas plant in Mors (Denmark) with animal manure as the main feedstock and 2% of household food waste addition. More information on the anaerobic digestion process is provided by [8]. The digestate was separated into a liquid and a solid fraction and the latter was dried and pelletized. The pellets were pyrolyzed in a pilot scale auger-type pyrolysis unit at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) at 600 °C, resulting in a digestate solids biochar (DS-C), with a biochar yield of about 40%. A part of the obtained biochar was afterwards post-oxidized in an oven at 550 °C overnight, resulting in a digestate solid ash (DS-A). The sewage sludge char (SS-C) was obtained from the VandCenterSyd wastewater treatment plant in Odense, Denmark. The treatment plant uses precipitation with ferric sulfate ($\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$) followed by biological P removal, then the sludge is anaerobically digested and dewatered before pyrolysis at a temperature of 600 °C [71]. The sewage sludge ash (SS-A) was obtained from the Biofos wastewater treatment plant in Avedøre, Denmark. The plant uses a combination of biological and chemical (FeClSO_4) P removal and the digested dewatered sewage sludge is mono-incinerated in a fluidized bed incinerator at a process temperature of 850 °C. Meat and bone meal, obtained from DAKA®, Denmark, was pyrolyzed in batches in an oven with a N_2 flushed reactor chamber for one hour at 600 °C to produce meat and bone meal biochar (MB-C). The frass biochar was derived from the residues of black soldier flies (*Hermetia illucens* L.) rearing and pyrolyzed at a process temperature of 500 °C. The poultry litter ash was purchased from the Dutch company BMC Moerdijk and had been produced from poultry litter in a fluidized bed at 750 °C. Prior to soil application, all materials were crushed and sieved to < 2 mm.

2.2. Characterization of the materials

All subsequently described analyses were performed in triplicate. All materials were analyzed for their elemental composition by ICP-OES (Agilent 5100, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA) after microwave digestion with HNO_3 , H_2O_2 and HF. Total C and N content was determined by elemental analysis (Vario macro cube, Elementar Analysensysteme GmbH, Germany). The pH of all materials was determined with a pH-meter after dispersion in MilliQ-water (1:25) for 1 h. Water extractable P (WEP) of the materials was analyzed after shaking in MQ-water (1:60) for 1 h and filtration (Whatman No.5 filter papers). In addition, P was extracted from the materials with NaHCO_3 (0.5 M) at a fertilizer:solution ratio of 1:1000 for 4 h (adapted from Duboc et al., 2022). All extracts were analyzed for ortho-P with a Flow Injection Analyzer (FIAsstar 5000, Foss Analytical, Sweden).

A simplified sequential extraction involving three steps and considering only inorganic P was additionally performed on all materials, except the frass biochar, based on Lemming et al. [44]. From each finely ground material, 0.35 g was first extracted with H_2O , followed by 0.1 M NaOH and 1 M HCl. After the addition of 35 ml of the extractant, the samples were shaken on an overhead shaker for 16 h. After centrifugation (5 min, 5000 rpm), the supernatant was filtered through Whatman No. 5 filter papers. The residual material on the filter paper was washed off with the subsequent extractant into the respective tubes. The ortho-P content of all extracts was analyzed by flow injection analysis. The P content of the different fractions was related to the total P content of the materials and the fraction of non-extracted P was referred to as residual P.

Table 1

Chemical properties, elemental composition, water and NaHCO₃-extractable phosphorus of ashes and biochars used in this study including standard errors. DS-A=Digestate ash, DS-C=Digestate biochar, IF-C=Insect frass biochar, MB-C=Meat and bone meal biochar, PL-A=Poultry litter ash, SS-A=Sewage sludge ash, SS-C=Sewage sludge biochar.

Material		DS-A	DS-C	IF-C	MB-C	PL-A	SS-A	SS-C
pH	(H ₂ O)	10.8 ± 0.0	11.2 ± 0.0	10.9 ± 0.0	11.2 ± 0.0	12.3 ± 0.2	8.6 ± 0.1	7.2 ± 0.1
C	%	0.4 ± 0.0	54.9 ± 0.7	60.1 ± 0.4	30.5 ± 1.3	1.2 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	18.1 ± 0.0
N		0.1 ± 0.0	1.9 ± 0.1	3.9 ± 0.1	5.2 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.9
P	g kg ⁻¹	81.3 ± 3.7	26.6 ± 1.5	36.5 ± 4.4	106.9 ± 2.1	57.5 ± 9.2	96.3 ± 8.2	69.8 ± 0.1
K		59.0 ± 2.5	20.2 ± 1.1	10.0 ± 1.7	5.0 ± 0.1	36.1 ± 6.1	16.3 ± 1.3	10.8 ± 0.1
Ca		135.3 ± 3.0	52.5 ± 1.0	22.5 ± 3.4	187.8 ± 2.5	136.0 ± 23.2	126.1 ± 20.1	83.7 ± 2.0
Mg		104.3 ± 9.2	43.7 ± 5.8	51.8 ± 5.8	25.0 ± 2.5	122.1 ± 26.5	14.9 ± 4.5	18.5 ± 3.7
Al		11.2 ± 0.5	5.4 ± 0.9	1.7 ± 0.4	1.7 ± 0.2	12.3 ± 1.5	30.9 ± 2.8	19.1 ± 1.6
Fe		67.7 ± 3.8	23.1 ± 1.3	3.5 ± 0.9	4.9 ± 0.5	6.3 ± 1.1	133.5 ± 17.6	124.2 ± 0.3
Zn		2.2 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.0	0.9 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1	2.2 ± 0.2	2.7 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.0
Cu	mg kg ⁻¹	759 ± 112	243 ± 6	127 ± 10	83 ± 25	472 ± 98	905 ± 156	721 ± 18.9
Cr		80.0 ± 3.3	30.9 ± 3.6	10.4 ± 2.4	21.2 ± 9.8	26.0 ± 1.6	106.3 ± 8.2	122.2 ± 43.4
Ni		36.6 ± 0.9	15.7 ± 0.3	8.1 ± 0.8	21.3 ± 2.3	29.3 ± 2.0	44.1 ± 2.2	46.8 ± 0.8
Cd		1.6 ± 0.0	1.0 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0	2.7 ± 0.1	5.3 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.4
(Fe+Al/P Ca/P	Molar ratio	0.5 ± 0.6	0.5 ± 0.5	0.1 ± 0.1	0.0 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 1.2	1.0 ± 0.0
		2.2 ± 1.1	2.6 ± 0.8	0.8 ± 1.0	2.3 ± 1.6	3.1 ± 3.3	1.7 ± 3.2	1.6 ± 0.7
WEP	% TP	0.0 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0	1.7 ± 0.3	0.3 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.9
NaHCO ₃		3.4 ± 0.3	4.4 ± 0.5	13.9 ± 2.1	1.0 ± 0.0	1.6 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.0

2.3. Acidification of materials using sulfuric acid

The acidification was tested with different H₂SO₄ concentrations (0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 5.0 M). For each concentration, 2.5 ml of H₂SO₄ was added to 5 g of material (1:2 (v/w)) in falcon tubes in triplicate. After addition, the material was mixed until all the material was moist and in contact with the acid. Shortly after mixing, the mixtures were dried for 24 h at 60 °C and subsequently analyzed for pH and WEP as described above. The H₂SO₄ concentration was increased up to 10 M for SS-A, SS-C, DS-A and PL-A. For the pot experiment, each material was acidified in a larger batch by applying H₂SO₄ in a concentration to obtain at least 30% WEP of the total P in each material. The acidified materials were crushed, sieved to < 2 mm and analyzed for total P, C and N content, WEP, pH, NaHCO₃-extractable P as described above.

2.4. XRD

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns were measured on dry and finely ground untreated and acidified materials using a PANalytical X'Pert Pro MPD powder diffractometer employing Co-K α radiation (K α 1 = 1.789 Å, 40 kV and 40 mA). Measurements were performed in continuous scan mode (2 θ range from 5° to 90°, step size 0.02°/step and 5 s/step, PW3011/10 detector). XRD data was analyzed with X'Pert HighScore.

2.5. Pot experiment

To determine plant P uptake from untreated and acidified materials, a pot experiment was conducted with maize as a test plant. An indirect isotope approach was used, where labile soil P is homogeneously labeled using ³³P and based on the isotopic dilution the P uptake from the fertilizer material is determined, see [25]. The pots were PVC tubes with a height of 28 cm and a diameter of 10 cm, resulting in a volume of 2.2 L. The soil used in the pot experiment was collected from the unfertilized treatment of the long-term field trial CRUCIAL at the University of Copenhagen's Experimental Farm Højbakkegård in Taastrup, Denmark [45]. The soil is a sandy loam (Luvisol) with 26% coarse sand, 44% fine sand, 14% silt, 13% clay, 3% organic matter and a pH (H₂O₁) of 6.4 [45]. The treatment had not received any fertilizer since 2003 and contained 11.2 mg P (kg soil)⁻¹ Olsen-P. Air-dried soil was sieved to 4 mm, weighed into a polyethylene bag and mixed with sand (25%, w/w), resulting in 2.5 kg DM per bag. The water-holding capacity (WHC) of the soil/sand mixture was determined by water saturation and subsequent

drainage on a saturated sand bed for 24 h and was found to be 24% (w/w). Before the addition of the labeling solution, P-free nutrient solutions were applied to the soil and homogeneously mixed. The nutrients were applied as NH₄NO₃ (150 mg N (kg soil)⁻¹), K₂SO₄ (150 mg K (kg soil)⁻¹), CaCl₂ (40 mg Ca (kg soil)⁻¹), MgSO₄x7H₂O (40 mg Mg (kg soil)⁻¹), CuSO₄x5H₂O (1.5 mg (kg soil)⁻¹), ZnSO₄x7H₂O (1.2 mg Zn (kg soil)⁻¹), Na₂MoO₄x2H₂O (0.1 mg Mo (kg soil)⁻¹), Iron(III)-EDTA (3 mg Fe (kg soil)⁻¹), H₃BO₃ (0.3 mg B (kg soil)⁻¹), MnSO₄xH₂O (3 mg Mn (kg soil)⁻¹). Three days later, the water content (WC) was adjusted to approximately 50% of the WHC and the soil was pre-incubated in plastic bags for one week at room temperature. After pre-incubation, 15 ml of a labeling solution containing carrier-free H₃³³PO₄ with an activity of 2.5 MBq was applied, corresponding to 1 MBq per kg of substrate. The soil was mixed with the labeling solution in a bowl for 2 min and afterwards incubated for another week to ensure near-equilibrium conditions for the naturally most abundant stable ³¹P and the radioactive ³³P [56]. On the day of sowing, untreated fertilizers were mixed into the soil at a rate of 80 mg P (kg soil)⁻¹ based on a previous experiment conducted with the same soil [54]. The acidified materials were added on a weight basis equal to the amount of the respective untreated material, thus, due to the dilution with H₂SO₄, a slightly smaller amount of total P was added per kg of soil (see Table 2 for the exact amounts added). The soil was then filled into the pots, which were lined with a thin plastic bag. To determine the crop's response to P fertilizer application a positive control receiving 80 mg P (kg soil)⁻¹ as triple super phosphate (TSP) and a negative control receiving no P fertilizer (0 P) were additionally set up. All treatments were replicated 4 times. Pots were placed in 4 blocks in a climate chamber with a 16 h day/8 h night period, temperature 20/15 °C day/night and daytime light of 600 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹. Three seeds of *Zea mays* L. cv. 'Ambition' (Limagrain SE) were sown in each pot at a depth of 4 cm. After emergence, the seedlings were thinned to one plant per pot. The pots were watered every second day by weight to 60% of WHC. At 21 days after sowing (DAS) and 27 DAS, a nitrogen top dressing of 80 mg N (kg soil)⁻¹ in the form of NH₄NO₃ was applied with the irrigation water. At 42 DAS and growth stage 18 (8 leaves unfolded) on the BBCH scale for maize for the positive control, the shoot biomass was harvested, dried at 60 °C and the dry weight was recorded. After drying, plant samples were milled and microwave-digested in HNO₃ and H₂O₂. The digested samples were analyzed by ICP-OES. The specific activity (SA) of plant digests was analyzed by liquid scintillation counting in a Packard TR 1900 (PerkinElmer, Waltham, USA). After harvest, two soil samples were taken from each pot vertically from the soil surface to a depth of 20

Table 2

Molarity H₂SO₄ used for acidification of materials and the pH (H₂O, 1:5), total P (TP) content, NaHCO₃ extractable P of the materials after acidification and amount of total P and WEP applied per kg of soil in the pot experiment including standard error. DS-A=Digestate ash, DS-C=Digestate biochar, IF-C=Insect frass biochar, MB-C=Meat and bone meal biochar, PL-A=Poultry litter ash, SS-A=Sewage sludge ash, SS-C=Sewage sludge biochar.

		DS-A	DS-C	IF-C	MB-C	PL-A	SS-A	SS-C
H ₂ SO ₄	M	7.5	5.0	2.5	5.0	10.0	10.0	10.0
pH	(H ₂ O)	4.8 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.0	2.4 ± 0.0	3.5 ± 0.0	3.1 ± 0.0	3.3 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.0
Total P	mg g ⁻¹	63.0 ± 0.9	27.0 ± 0.0	32.0 ± 0.0	85.0 ± 0.6	48.0 ± 0.0	75.0 ± 0.5	46.0 ± 4.6
N	%	0.0 ± 0.0	1.0 ± 0.0	2.7 ± 0.4	3.9 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.0	0.1 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0
C	%	0.2 ± 0.0	45.1 ± 1.0	55.3 ± 5.9	26.4 ± 1.0	0.3 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	11.1 ± 0.6
NaHCO ₃ -P	% TP	10.3 ± 0.0	19.2 ± 0.5	19.5 ± 0.8	18.3 ± 1.5	11.6 ± 0.3	6.1 ± 0.2	2.7 ± 0.4
P applied	mg (kg soil) ⁻¹	62.0 ± 0.9	75.2 ± 0.0	71.0 ± 0.1	63.0 ± 0.5	66.0 ± 0.1	62.0 ± 0.4	53.0 ± 5.3
WEP applied	mg (kg soil) ⁻¹	19.2 ± 0.9	50.1 ± 0.3	43.4 ± 6.3	45.3 ± 0.5	43.8 ± 2.5	27.3 ± 2.0	22.7 ± 2.0

cm using an auger. The soil samples were air-dried and pH was measured after 1 h dispersion in MilliQ-water (1:5) and on FIA (see above) soil water extractable P (WEP) was analyzed after shaking in MQ-water (1:60) for 1 h and Olsen-P after 30 min extraction with NaHCO₃ (0.5 M) (1:20).

2.6. Calculations

The contribution of P from the fertilizer (P_{df}) was calculated from the specific activity of the maize plant receiving no P fertilization (SA_{plant0P}) and the specific activity of the maize plant receiving P fertilizer:

$$P_{df} = \left(1 - \frac{SA_{plant+P}}{SA_{plant0P}}\right) \times P \text{ uptake}_{plant+P} \quad (1)$$

To correct for P derived from maize seeds, the equation given by Pypers et al. [58] was used to calculate the fraction of seed P translocated to the shoots based on the shoot P content. Their equation is based on the P shoot content of maize seedlings with varying P supply grown in P-free sand:

$$P_{dfseed} = 0.715 \times P_{seed} \times \left(1 - e^{(-1.973 \times P_{shoot})}\right) \quad (2)$$

The mineral fertilizer equivalent (MFE) value was calculated based on the P_{df} of the treatments, the mineral P80 control (optimal fertilizer dose) and the amount of P applied:

$$MFE = \frac{P_{df} \text{ treatment}}{P_{df80P}} \times 100$$

2.7. Statistical analyses

Statistical analysis was performed using the R programming environment for statistical computing [59]. A linear mixed model was fitted with block as a random effect and materials and pre-treatment as the main effects, and tested for variance homogeneity and normal distribution. Data for shoot biomass, P uptake and plant Al, Cu, and Zn contents had to be log transformed to achieve a normal distribution. A two-way ANOVA was performed and means were compared with Tukey's HSD test (<0.05) and Student's T-tests (<0.05). The means of the treatments were compared with the control mean using Dunnett's test. Linear regression was performed for correlations between plant P uptake and WEP and bicarbonate extractable P of the fertilizer materials and tested by the non-parametric Spearman's Rank-Order correlation.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effects of acidification on P solubility and P speciation

In the sequential extraction, a major fraction (50–80%) of the P in all materials was HCl-extractable (Fig. 1). Poultry litter ash had the largest fraction of acid-extractable P, followed by digestate ash and sewage sludge ash. The residual P was highest for meat and bone meal biochar

Fig. 1. Extractable P (% of total P content) from the materials in a sequential extraction in the order of H₂O, NaOH and HCl and residual P (Total P- Extracted P). Error bars represent the standard error. DS-A=Digestate ash, DS-C=Digestate biochar, MB-C=Meat and bone meal biochar, PL-A=Poultry litter ash, SS-A=Sewage sludge ash, SS-C=Sewage sludge biochar.

(43%), followed by digestate biochar (37%) and lowest for poultry litter ash (15%). Only sewage sludge biochar had a significant fraction of NaOH-extractable P with 14%, while for all other materials this was less than 1%.

The high acid-extractable fraction can be explained by the fact that all untreated materials showed peaks matching XRD reflections of hydroxyapatite (Fig. 3), which is an acid-soluble P species [38]. In general, phase identification in XRD patterns was challenging due to the complex elemental composition of the materials (Table 1), many overlapping peaks, as well the presence of both broad peaks (i.e., less crystalline phases) and low signal-to-noise ratios (i.e., low phase abundance). In addition, a large variety of phosphate phases exist and they can contain many different elements and mixtures, resulting in different XRD patterns, making unambiguous phase identification difficult. Despite these challenges, some phases could be identified (Fig. 3). Non-phosphate-bearing crystalline compounds detected were silica (SiO₂) in all materials, carbonate in some of them and hematite in the sludge ash.

Based on the differences in speciation, the pH change and P release differed between the materials (Fig. 2). The pH of the insect frass biochar, the digestate biochar and meat and bone meal biochar already dropped below 4 at 1 M, 2 M and 2.5 M respectively and more than 50% of TP was extractable and therefore the concentration was not increased further. On the other hand, especially the ashes derived from digestate and poultry litter exhibited a very strong buffer capacity, thus requiring higher acid concentrations. Based on the titration curves, different acid concentrations were selected for the acidification of the materials to be used in the pot experiment (Table 2). The acidification diluted the total N, C and P content of the materials due to the mass of sulfuric acid added. However, the P content of the acidified digestate biochar did not

Fig. 2. Water extractable P (% total initial P content) and pH (measured in H₂O) in relation to different sulfuric acid concentrations applied to the materials (1:2 (v/w)). Error bars represent the standard error. DS-A=Digestate ash, DS-C=Digestate biochar, IF-C=Insect frass biochar, MB-C=Meat and bone meal biochar, PL-A=Poultry litter ash, SS-A=Sewage sludge ash, SS-C=Sewage sludge biochar.

change compared to the original material, although it showed a clear reduction in total N and C. This may be due to measurement inaccuracies. The acid treatment generally led to complete removal or a reduction of the amount of hydroxyapatite in the materials, and the formation of anhydrite, along with some form of Ca phosphate phase with/without Al and/or K, depending on the material elemental composition (Fig. 3). Acid treatment had little impact on silica and hematite, but led to the removal of carbonate.

3.1.1. Sewage sludge ash

The water-extractable and HCl pools were similar to other studies, where different sewage sludge ashes showed a very low water-extractable fraction and HCl-P as the largest pool, usually extracting more than half of the total P [33,44]. However, the NaOH extractable fraction in our study was much lower compared to the 4–33% TP in the sequential extractions from the aforementioned studies. Despite the addition of FeClSO₄ for P removal in the wastewater treatment plant, the

Ca/P ratio was similar to the Al+Fe/P ratio. Sludge ash can contain various P species such as calcium phosphates, hydroxyapatite, Ca-Al-phosphates, Ca-Fe-phosphates, Ca-Mg-phosphates (whitlockite), Al and Fe phosphates and K phosphates [36,42,50,56]. In our case, in accordance with the molar ratios, the XRD spectra showed peaks for Ca- and Al-associated P (Fig. 3). The sludge materials were the only materials containing an Al phosphate phase. The sewage sludge ash showed a gradually increasing WEP and decreasing pH up to a pH of 1.8 and a WEP of 30% of TP (Fig. 2) which could indicate the solubilization of the different P species at different pH levels. After the acidification, Ca-phosphates were identified in the ash, explaining the increased water solubility, which is similar to results of Weigand et al. [72] who found that phosphoric acid treatment of sludge ash forms soluble calcium and magnesium dihydrogen phosphate. Potentially, amorphous Al phosphates could have formed after acidification, which are not detectable by XRD [42].

Fig. 3. X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns of the untreated and acidified (+) materials. Only relevant phases are annotated in the figure. For PL-A no relevant peaks were identified. DS-A=Digestate ash, DS-C=Digestate biochar, IF-C=Insect frass biochar, MB-C=Meat and bone meal biochar, PL-A=Poultry litter ash, SS-A=Sewage sludge ash, SS-C=Sewage sludge biochar; + = acidified material.

3.1.2. Sewage sludge biochar

The sewage sludge biochar was the only material that contained considerable amounts of NaOH extractable P, which according to the original Hedley sequential extraction indicates Al and Fe-bound P [29]. Mackay et al. [52] found a slightly larger NaOH extractable pool of 18% of TP in a full sequential fractionation with sewage sludge biochar. The slightly higher Al+Fe/P ratio and the lower temperature during pyrolysis compared to combustion may retain Fe and Al phosphates, while at higher temperatures during incineration and in the presence of Ca, Fe or Al phosphates can be transformed into apatite P [48,50]. In contrast to the sludge ash, the titration of the sewage sludge biochar showed a P release mainly below pH 3 rather than a gradual increase, which could indicate the solubilization of Fe/Al phosphates at a lower pH rather than the solubilization of hydroxyapatite [57]. The XRD spectra showed the presence of AlPO_4 next to hydroxyapatite at a lower intensity (Fig. 3). Potentially, the solubilization of apatite-P in the presence of Al can lead to the formation of Al-P which could then only be dissolved at a pH of < 3, similar to what Lee & Kim [42] and Petzet et al. [57] observed in sludge ash. There may also be XRD-undetectable amorphous Al/Fe-phosphates (Al/Fe-P) present in the biochar [50].

3.1.3. Poultry litter ash

The very high HCl extractable fraction for poultry litter ash is comparable to the results of Codling [12], who measured a very similar HCl fraction (82%) on average for three different poultry litter ash samples. We found apatite in the poultry litter ash, as commonly reported in the literature [22,37,75]. The high content of apatite P and the high acid solubility of apatite explain the large fraction of HCl-extractable P in poultry litter ash [38]. In addition, peaks corresponding to a K-phosphate or K-Al phosphate phase were detected in the untreated poultry litter ash (Fig. 3). Poultry litter ash is rich in carbonates and is known to have a strong buffer capacity [75]. According to the titration curve, the P species in the poultry litter ash were readily soluble already at a higher pH, but due to the high buffer capacity and acid consumption, high concentrations were required to solubilize P. Probably due to the high potassium content, potassium sulfate was formed with acidification (Fig. 3).

3.1.4. Digestate biochar

The only crystalline P species in the digestate biochar detected by XRD was hydroxyapatite, which is in accordance with other studies where hydroxyapatite, but also dicalcium and tricalcium phosphate,

were dominant P species in digestate biochar at temperatures above 600 °C [6,7]. Digestate biochar had a high initial pH, but a low buffer capacity and P release already at higher pH is consistent with readily acid-soluble apatite P. This is also confirmed by the removal of apatite with the acidification as seen in the XRD spectrum (Fig. 3). Luo et al. [49] also observed a complete solubilization of apatite-P from digestate biochar with only a minor content of non-apatite inorganic P remaining in the biochar after acid leaching. Similarly, in this study, the acidification with 5 M potentially removed all acid-extractable P species, as is indicated by the WEP fraction of the acidified material being as high as the HCl-fraction in the sequential extraction.

3.1.5. Digestate ash

As for the biochar, the XRD spectrum indicated the presence of hydroxyapatite in the digestate ash. Despite the presence of apatite in the material, high acid concentrations were required to solubilize a substantial amount of P. This may be related to a strong buffer capacity, already previously observed with gasification ash from digested pig slurry [39]. The WEP of the digestate ash increased to 55% of TP with a pH shift from 1.9 to 1.5 (Fig. 2). Similar to the sludge biochar, the solubilized apatite P could form Al phosphate with the Al present in the ash which is then only solubilized at a pH below 2 [57].

3.1.6. Insect frass biochar

The insect frass biochar showed a release of P from around pH 7 and an almost linear decrease in pH and increase in WEP with increasing acid concentration up to 2 M (Fig. 2). This could be related to the low Ca/P and Al+Fe/P ratios and their implications for a different P speciation than in the other materials. According to the XRD, the untreated insect frass biochar was the only material containing a Ca phosphate phase that is soluble in water [38]. The content of soluble Ca phosphate could explain the higher WEP of the untreated biochar and also its higher fertilizer value compared to the other materials (see below).

3.1.7. Meat and bone meal biochar

Similar to our study, Glæsner et al. [26] found low crystalline apatite in bone char and only at temperatures above 750 °C, more crystalline apatite was formed. Bekiaris et al. [6] also found hydroxyapatite and calcium phosphates in bone meal biochars. The speciation explains the release of P with lower acid inputs (Fig. 2). The meat and bone meal biochar showed a very large increase in WEP already at 1.5 and 2 M, when the pH changed from 5.4 to 4.8. The removal of the water-insoluble apatite and the formation of magnesium phosphates as seen in the XRD spectra explains the increase in WEP (Fig. 3). As for the digestate biochar, most of the HCl-fraction was solubilized with the use of 5 M SA.

Fig. 4. a) Maize shoot biomass (g pot^{-1}), b) P uptake from soil and fertilizer (mg pot^{-1}), c) P recovery (% of applied P) and d) mineral fertilizer equivalent (MFE %). Letters indicate significant differences between untreated and corresponding acidified material. In case of P uptake letters indicate differences between fertilizer derived P. Error bars represent standard errors. Asterisks indicate a significant difference to the mineral fertilizer control treatment according to Dunnett's test. In the case of P uptake, asterisks indicate differences between fertilizer-derived P in the P80 control. DS-A=Digestate ash, DS-C=Digestate biochar, IF-C=Insect frass biochar, MB-C=Meat and bone meal biochar, PL-A=Poultry litter ash, SS-A=Sewage sludge ash, SS-C=Sewage sludge biochar; + = acidified material.

Considering the sequential extraction and titration curves, we found that acidification is an effective approach to increase P solubility and thus confirm hypothesis 1. Based on the XRD spectra, we conclude that the acidification solubilized mainly hydroxyapatite-P or other amorphous P species, followed by the formation of Ca phosphates, more soluble amorphous P species or ortho-P adsorbed to the material surface (Fig. 3). However, the efficiency of the acidification cannot be directly related to the materials' Ca/P ratio, because also buffer capacity and speciation of Ca phosphates or their crystallinity play an important role. Digestate, meat and bone meal and insect frass biochar responded well to acidification, with a major fraction of P solubilized already with lower acid inputs.

3.2. Pot experiment

3.2.1. P availability from untreated materials

Application of the untreated materials, except insect frass biochar, did not significantly increase maize shoot biomass in the pot experiment compared to the unfertilized control (Fig. 4). The P recovery of the SS-C, MB-C and SS-A was below 1%. The PL-A and DS-C had a P recovery of 1.7%, the DS-A of 2.2 and the IF-C with 4.3% had the highest P recovery among the untreated materials. P recovery from the mineral fertilizer control TSP was 21%. The MFE value was between 2% and 8% for all untreated materials except for the insect frass biochar (18%), which shows that none of the untreated materials except the insect frass biochar had a significant P fertilizer effect prior to acidification. This result is consistent with the very low WEP and bicarbonate-extractable P of the untreated materials and highlights the very low short-term P effect of thermally treated products and the need for some form of processing or pre-treatment if used as a P fertilizer. Nevertheless, a trend towards higher P availability from untreated materials derived from animal excreta (digestate ash and biochar, insect frass biochar and poultry litter ash) was observed, confirming the findings of Glaser & Lehr [27] in their meta-analysis.

The P availability of the untreated digestate biochar was lower than reported in the literature. In an experiment by Ayaz et al. (2022), digestate biochar increased P uptake by 69% compared to the unfertilized control in a pot experiment, and an increasing effect on biomass was also found in a field experiment [30]. The untreated digestate ash performed similarly to the biochar, which is consistent with results from other studies [40,41]. Meat and bone meal biochar from low-temperature pyrolysis at a low soil pH can increase plant available P [26]. However, in this experiment, the untreated meat and bone meal biochar did not have a significant fertilizing effect, nor did the untreated poultry litter ash, which is in contrast to the results of Bachmann & Eichler-Löbermann [4] and Yusiharni et al. [76]. The low effect of both materials in this study can probably be attributed to a near-neutral soil pH. Both sewage sludge biochar and ash showed a very low availability of P and MFE, which is commonly observed [43,52,70,74]. Overall, the insect frass biochar was the only untreated material with a significant P fertilizer effect.

3.2.2. P availability from acidified materials

Several studies [17,2,5] have been conducted on "acid-activated" or "acidified" biochars, which are pre-treated materials aimed at reducing emissions or increasing the sorption capacity for certain compounds. P-rich biochars are not commonly used in these studies and, most importantly, the acid pre-treatment usually includes a washing step to remove the acid. In this study, we used a different acidification approach with the main goal of increasing the P fertilizer value of biochars and ashes.

Acidification increased shoot biomass between 1.4 and 3.5 times compared to the untreated material control (Fig. 4a). All acidified material treatments showed a higher total P uptake than the unfertilized control, but both shoot biomass and P uptake were still less than half that of the mineral-fertilized control (Fig. 4a, b). For all materials except

the insect frass biochar, acidification resulted in a higher fertilizer-derived P uptake compared to the corresponding untreated material (Fig. 4b). P uptake from the acidified materials was highest with the digestate biochar followed by insect frass biochar, poultry litter ash, sewage sludge ash, digestate ash, meat and bone meal biochar and sewage sludge biochar. The increasing effect of acidification was evident even though a slightly smaller amount of P was applied in the treatments with acidified materials.

The results for P recovery and MFE, taking into account the different P application rates, support this conclusion as well (Fig. 4c, d). The P recovery from the acidified materials and TSP ranked in the following order TSP (21%) > DS-C (10.4%) > SS-A (9.1%) > PL-A (8.9%) > IF-C (8.7%) > DS-A (7.0%) > SS-C (6.6%) > MB-C (6.5%) (Fig. 4c). In all cases, the P recovery was significantly increased compared to the untreated material by acidification. The MFE value of the different acidified materials did not differ significantly and ranged from 25% to 39%, with digestate ash having the lowest and digestate biochar having the highest MFE (Fig. 4d). Overall, the different acid concentrations used for the acidification resulted in a similar P recovery and MFE for all acidified materials following the observed increase in WEP from the materials.

Based on that, both water-extractable and sodium bicarbonate-extractable P and were good predictors of plant-available P from biochars and ashes (Fig. 5). However, WEP showed only minimal differences between the untreated biochars and ashes, although there were larger differences in the pot experiment. Thus, the correlation with bicarbonate P was better overall. Bicarbonate-extractable P has already been shown to be a good indicator of plant P availability from waste products [19,10]. Our results confirm that bicarbonate extraction is a good predictor for P availability from biochars and ashes in soils with a near-neutral pH.

Acidification also increased the amount of P taken up from the soil compared to the unfertilized control and the untreated materials (Fig. 4), which was probably due to increased root growth and consequently better soil exploration. The application of acidified materials could also have led to increased solubilization of non-labile soil P, which we would not have been able to distinguish from the non-labeled fertilizer P with the isotopic dilution approach. However, the soil pH was not drastically decreased after application of the acidified materials, and the acidified materials with the lowest pH levels did not consistently result in the highest plant P uptake. In addition, the strong correlation between the WEP and bicarbonate extractions and P uptake underlines that the solubilization of P during the pre-treatment is the major driver of the P fertilizer effect and that there is no or very little secondary solubilization of P from the material or soil after application (Fig. 5). Sica et al. [62] applied acidified sludge ash to the same soil as used in this experiment and found that the application of acidified material did not solubilize soil P, and also Akanji et al. [3] did not observe soil P solubilization after the application of acidified biochar with a pH of 3.

The acidified sludge biochar had the lowest proportion of WEP despite a 10 M acidification, resulting in the lowest MFE of the acidified materials. The acidification of sludge ash was slightly more effective at the same acid concentration, leading to a more than threefold increase in P uptake. Acid digestion of sludge ash or partial replacement of rock phosphate with sludge ash in TSP production showed that sludge ash with acid treatment can increase P availability from sludge ash [28,72], due to a rapid P release and diffusion into the soil [62]. The acidification of poultry litter ash was also effective and increased the MFE similarly to the other materials. Similarly, Komiyama et al. [37] observed that sulfuric acid addition to a compound fertilizer containing poultry litter ash resulted in an increase in P uptake and a P fertilizer value as high as the mineral control. The application of acidified digestate ash provided the lowest amount of WEP per kg of soil of all materials and consequently, the increase compared to the untreated materials was not significant. A better fertilizer effect could probably be achieved with a higher acid input. However, digestate ash did not show any advantages over the pyrolyzed material in this study, neither in terms of the initial P fertilizer

Fig. 5. Linear regression, Spearman correlation (R) and p-value of water extractable P (WEP) (mg applied / g soil) and bicarbonate extractable P (mg applied / g soil) with fertilizer-derived P (mg/pot) in the growth trial.

value nor acidification potential. The acidified digestate biochar had the highest MFE of all treatments, which was achieved with the second lowest acid concentration. The acidification also significantly increased P availability from the meat and bone meal biochar. Zimmer et al. [77] observed that acidification from pH 8.6 to pH 4.0 by sulfur enrichment of bone char increased P recovery from less than 3% to 15% compared to the untreated material. In our experiment, despite the application of a high amount of WEP in the acidification treatment, the bone char had one of the lowest MFEs compared to some of the other materials. This is also underlined by the fact that the meat and bone meal biochar was the only acidified material that was far from the overall regression line between WEP and P uptake from the fertilizer. A possible explanation for this could be the re-adsorption of P onto the biochar, as ortho-P dissolved from apatite, the only P species found in the meat and bone meal biochar has been shown to be re-adsorbed onto positively charged hydroxyapatite surfaces at pH > 4 [16]. The P fertilizer value of the insect frass biochar was even further increased despite the lowest input of acid, but due to the already higher P uptake from the untreated frass biochar, the difference was not significant.

At the end of the pot experiment, all acidified materials resulted in a higher soil WEP and Olsen-P content than in the negative control soil (Table 3). The untreated sewage sludge biochar treatment had the lowest WEP content, so only for sewage sludge biochar was there a difference between pre-treated and untreated biochar. For Olsen-P, there were much larger differences and for all materials except

digestate ash and insect frass biochar, the acidified material resulted in significantly higher Olsen-P values compared to the corresponding untreated materials. This could imply that acidification does not only increase the immediate P fertilizer effect, but also the residual P effect of ashes and biochars. Based on the results, we can confirm hypothesis 3 that acidification efficiently increases the P fertilizer value of biochars and ashes. The economic viability of the approach needs to be assessed though. However, the technical parameters for the acidification process, such as liquid:solid ratio, type and amount of acid used and different drying temperatures, need to be tested and optimized before a proper economic evaluation can be made. In terms of acid input and fertilizer equivalent value, the digestate and meat and bone meal biochar were the most responsive to acidification. The highest increase with acidification was observed with the sludge materials, but only at much higher acid inputs.

3.2.3. Effects of acidification on heavy metal uptake

All biochars and ashes, except the sludge ash, were below the Danish limit values for HM content in waste materials used in agriculture [53] and could therefore be legally applied as a fertilizer (Table 1). The sludge ash was 6 mg above the limit value of 100 mg Cr kg⁻¹. All plant concentrations were within the range of typical heavy metal concentrations in plants and well below toxic levels indicating that the materials did not drastically increase HM uptake [55]. For all materials except the sludge biochar, there was a trend towards lower Cd

Table 3

Soil pH, water extractable P (WEP) and Olsen-P after harvest. Letters indicate significant differences between treatments. Asterisks indicate significant differences compared to the unfertilized control. DS-A=Digestate ash, DS-C=Digestate biochar, IF-C=Insect frass biochar, MB-C=Meat and bone meal biochar, PL-A=Poultry litter ash, SS-A=Sewage sludge ash, SS-C=Sewage sludge biochar.

Treatment	pH		WEP	mg P (kg soil) ⁻¹		Olsen-P	mg P (kg soil) ⁻¹	
C-0	6.3	± 0.1	4.9	± 1.8		9.0	± 2.0	
TSP	6.4	± 0.2	13.1	± 2.6		40.4	± 7.8	
IF-C	6.5	± 0.1	9.3	± 0.7	ab*	14.4	± 1.5	cde*
+ IF-C	6.2	± 0.1	9.1	± 0.7	ab*	17.9	± 1.9	bcd*
MB-C	6.3	± 0.1	6.8	± 3.4	bcd	10.2	± 0.8	ef
+ MB-C	6.2	± 0.1	8.7	± 1.1	abc*	18.1	± 2.9	bc*
DS-C	6.6	± 0.2	7.5	± 2.1	abcd	12.5	± 0.9	ef
+ DS-C	6.2	± 0.1	11.3	± 0.4	ab*	21.5	± 2.8	ab*
DS-A	6.7	± 0.1	13.0	± 1.7	a*	13.1	± 2.3	f
+ DS-A	6.3	± 0.2	12.7	± 1.3	abcd	18.8	± 3.4	def*
SS-A	6.2	± 0.1	7.3	± 3.1	abcd	10.8	± 0.9	ef
+ SS-A	6.2	± 0.2	10.0	± 2.2	ab*	20.1	± 1.6	ab*
SS-C	6.2	± 0.2	4.1	± 0.6	d	9.6	± 2.6	ef
+ SS-C	6.1	± 0.1	11.8	± 1.6	ab*	24.9	± 1.6	a*
PL-A	6.5	± 0.1	8.1	± 2.3	abcd	12.0	± 1.4	ef
+ PL-A	6.3	± 0.2	10.0	± 1.0	ab*	20.4	± 3.4	ab*

concentrations with acidified compared to untreated materials, which was significant for sludge ash and the digestate biochar and probably due to dilution following the increase in biomass (Fig. 6).

The uptake of Cd, Cu and Zn was expressed as uptake per mg of P taken up to correct for the increase in biomass in the acidification treatments (Fig. 6). The sludge biochar was the only material where more Cd was taken up per unit P in the acidified compared to the untreated treatment, but the difference was not significant. Together with the observed insignificant increase in Cd concentration with acidification, this could indicate that acidification slightly increased Cd availability from sludge biochar, but no clear conclusions can be drawn due to the high variability of the data. Notably, this cannot be related to the amount of Cd applied as the sludge ash, poultry litter ash and digestate biochar had the highest Cd/P ratios and therefore the highest Cd application rates.

Plant Cu concentrations were significantly lower in all acidified treatments compared to the untreated ones, except for the insect frass biochar, which could be due to the smaller increase in biomass with the acidification of the frass biochar. The Cu uptake per mg P was always higher with the untreated materials compared to the pre-treated ones. Based on these results, we assume that Cu availability was not increased by acidification.

For Zn concentrations, the differences between untreated and acidified materials were less pronounced. In most cases, Zn concentrations were not significantly decreased with acidification despite the increase in shoot biomass. Only for the digestate biochar and the sludge ash, which resulted in the highest shoot biomasses among the acidified materials, there was a significantly lower Zn concentration after acidification. With an increase in P uptake and no change in Zn availability, a decrease in Zn uptake per unit P was expected. However, only the

digestate biochar, sludge ash and poultry litter ash showed this decrease with acidification. Based on the results we can speculate that the acidification increased Zn availability. This is in line with Sigurnjak et al. [63], who found that acidification increased the Zn uptake of lettuce from different manure and digestate-based fertilizers and suggested that acidification could play a future role in biofortification. The difference in dilution effects did not follow the total amount of Zn and Cu applied, suggesting that the Zn and Cu release after acidification is related to the speciation of Zn or Cu in the materials.

Overall, these results support that there is no clear increase in Cu and Cd uptake with the acidification of biochars and ashes, and possibly an increase in Zn uptake. Therefore, hypothesis 4 on an increased HM uptake after acidification can be rejected for Cu and Cd, but not for Zn. However, investigations of HM availability in soils after the application of acidified materials are still needed.

3.2.4. Effects of acidification on soil pH

Ashes and biochars can increase soil pH depending on their alkalinity and the initial soil pH and buffer capacity [23]. In this experiment, based on their P content, only small amounts of biochar or ashes were applied. There was only a significant increase in soil pH compared to the control in the treatments that received untreated digestate biochar and ash (Table 3), which are known to have a high liming potential [15,65]. After the acidification, the digestate materials did not show any liming effect (Table 3) due to the elimination of carbonates during acidification as seen in the XRD spectra (Fig. 3). Compared to the control, there was a trend towards lower soil pH in the treatments with acidified material, but these differences were not significant. The acidified sludge biochar was the only material that decreased soil pH by more than 0.1 units compared to the negative control due to the low pH of the acidified

Fig. 6. Cd, Cu and Zn concentration in plant material ($\mu\text{g (g plant material)}^{-1}$) and plant uptake of Cd, Cu and Zn per mg P taken up. Error bars represent standard errors. Letters indicate significant differences between untreated and acidified material. Asterisks indicate a significant difference to the mineral fertilizer control treatment according to Dunnett's test. DS-A=Digestate ash, DS-C=Digestate biochar, IF-C=Insect frass biochar, MB-C=Meat and bone meal biochar, PL-A=Poultry litter ash, SS-A=Sewage sludge ash, SS-C=Sewage sludge biochar; + = acidified material.

sludge biochar.

Although the effect on soil pH depends on the type and amount of acid used, application rates, biochar or ash properties and soil characteristics, we can conclude that, contrary to our hypothesis, a clear effect on P availability can be achieved with an acidification pre-treatment without drastically changing soil pH. In addition to the effect on soil pH and HM availability, other possible acidification-induced changes in biochar characteristics such as carbon stability or sorption behavior and effects on soil biology should also be investigated to determine how acidified biochars can contribute to soil quality improvement and carbon sequestration.

4. Conclusions

The acidification of biochars and ashes significantly increased their P fertilizer value. However, the amount of acid required to achieve this effect varied depending on the buffer capacity and P speciation of the materials. For materials that contain mainly apatite and have a low buffer capacity, acidification effectively solubilized P. Thus, the meat and bone meal and digestate biochar required less acid, while materials derived from the thermal treatment of sewage sludge required more acid, but also showed the highest increase in P fertilizer value compared to the respective untreated materials. The application of acidified materials neither decreased soil pH nor increased plant Cd or Cu uptake. This study highlights that acidification can potentially become an effective approach to increase P availability from biochars and ashes. Therefore, it could facilitate P recycling from various thermally treated waste products.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Clara Kopp: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Pietro Sica:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Changyong Lu:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Dominique Tobler:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Lars Stoumann Jensen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Dorette Müller-Stöver:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

All data is openly available online in ERDA, the repository of the University of Copenhagen.

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